

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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RI4C2 PROJECT

Tools and resources guidebook

RI4C2 PROJECT GUIDEBOOK
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I. Introduction

This document aims at informing researchers and stakeholders of the EC2U Alliance partner universities about activities led within the framework of the RI4C2 project (Research & Innovation for Cities & Citizens) and how they can benefit from it. Firstly, this document introduces the EC2U Alliance, which initiated the RI4C2 project. Then, an overview of the characteristics and objectives of the RI4C2 project is given. Finally, the document presents the concrete activities led within each Work Package (WP) of the project and their associated resources.

II. Context

A. EC2U

The European Campus of City-Universities (EC2U) is a multicultural and multilingual Alliance initially consisting of seven long-standing, education- and research-led, locally and globally engaged universities from diverse regions of the European Union: the University of Coimbra (Portugal), the University of Iasi (Romania), the University of Jena (Germany), the University of Pavia (Italy), the University of Poitiers (France, coordinator), the University of Salamanca (Spain) and the University of Turku (Finland). The Johannes Kepler University of Linz joined the Alliance on November 1st, 2023.

Figure 1 : Map of the EC2U Alliance members

The EC2U Alliance now forms a community of 200 000 students and 25 000 staff members, in direct reach of more than 2 000 000 citizens. The Alliance's ambition is to develop an open and innovative space allowing free mobility of students and staff members among the eight universities and associated cities, thus overcoming clichéd views of regional and national identities.

This objective will be reached with the creation of a pan-European campus, connected by a sense of shared European identity, and developing a smart higher education ecosystem through a new model of quality education for an inclusive society. This unique model relies on a cooperation between universities and cities, involving academic communities (students, teachers, researchers, administrative staff), municipalities, higher education regulatory bodies, local authorities, socio-economic entities and citizens.

The EC2U Alliance is committed to advancing four Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of the United Nations:

- SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being
- SDG 4: Quality Education
- SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities
- SDG 16: Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions

B. The RI4C2 project

The “Research & Innovation for Cities & Citizens – RI4C2” project was submitted by the EC2U Alliance in the Horizon 2020 “Science with & for Society” (SwafS) call for European Universities in autumn 2020. It was selected by the European Commission for a period of 3 years (2021-2024). The specific objectives of the RI4C2 project are to extend the activities of EC2U to the Research and Innovation (R&I) fields to create a Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE).

The project develops a process that involves a gradual and adaptative transformation of all aspects of the R&I missions at the participating universities. The RI4C2 project activities and deliverables will nurture the “consolidation phase” of the EC2U Alliance that has just started (2023-2027).

The objectives of the RI4C2 project are the following:

- Developing a common R&I agenda, including the creation of new Virtual Institutes
- Strengthening human capital by supporting researchers' careers and encouraging gender equality in research
- Sharing research infrastructures and resources
- Reinforcing cooperation with non-academic actors
- Mainstreaming Open Science
- Promoting Citizen Science
- Promoting cooperation among Alliances of European Universities

III. WP1 – Transformation management

WP1 not only takes care of the regular management of the RI4C2 project, it also aims at accompanying the members of the EC2U Alliance in a process that will lead to a true transformation of their R&I strategy. The aim is to enrich the existing individual R&I strategies with all the results and tools of the RI4C2 project and making the joint EC2U R&I agenda a reality. Also, due to the specific context of the European Universities initiative, special attention is paid to ensuring a constant dialogue between the actors of the EC2U Erasmus+ project and of the RI4C2 project. It is this combination between the two projects that will enable the creation of the proposed Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE).

A. Recommendations for the creation of a network of platforms

One of the goals of WP1 is to study the feasibility of developing shared R&I platforms both from governance and financial viewpoints, establishing a list of potential obstacles (regulatory, financial, political, etc.). A detailed analysis of the organisation and regulations of R&I platforms at each partner university was presented, while also looking at the national and European regulations in order to provide recommendations for the future creation of an EC2U network for shared R&I platforms. The main findings led to outlining some short and mid-term recommendations for setting up such an Alliance network.

There are various barriers to the creation of an EC2U network of shared R&I platforms. The recommendations provided correspond to different levels of difficulty in terms of implementation. A first set of short-term recommendations was made related to communication and fostering networking. A second set of recommendations was made but with more political implications and more mid to long-term perspectives, i.e., “systemic recommendations”.

1) Short-term recommendations

Two short-term recommendations were formulated, which will constitute the first steps towards creating an EC2U network. Firstly, increasing communication on all the existing platforms in each EC2U partner university would allow all researchers of the EC2U community to be aware of all the platforms available in the Alliance. Secondly, it was recommended that all partner universities start using the OpenIRIS platform. Indeed, it allows to centralise and increase the visibility of R&I platforms at the university and it enables to reduce the time dedicated to

administrative tasks for platform managers. Using OpenIRIS at all EC2U universities could facilitate collaborations between researchers of the EC2U Alliance and the development of common research projects via the use of R&I platforms.

2) Systemic recommendations

A first systemic recommendation is for all partner universities to institutionally organise the governance of their platforms to facilitate general access to platforms for EC2U universities. This organisational structure would enable partner universities to establish specific conditions facilitating access to the platforms within EC2U. A second recommendation would be to sign an agreement between the partner universities to create the EC2U network for shared R&I platforms. If an agreement were to be signed to facilitate access to the platforms, it should also include the standardisation of costs for the access and use of platforms for the EC2U partners (this could work hand in hand with the use of OpenIRIS). Once this step is achieved, the EC2U partner universities could proceed to include EC2U standardised costs within the agreement creating the EC2U network for shared R&I platforms.

Such systemic change would genuinely facilitate the creation of an EC2U shared R&I platforms network, at the service of all the internal R&I communities and external EC2U partners.

IV. WP2 – EC2U R&I Agenda

The seven universities participating in the EC2U Alliance are determined to gradually align their R&I strategies to converge towards a common R&I agenda that will be much more than the sum of their individual strategies. The aim is to develop a demand-driven, transparent, inclusive and interdisciplinary EC2U R&I Agenda shaped together by universities, cities, citizens and socioeconomic/sociocultural stakeholders. The common agenda will significantly broaden the scope of R&I capacity and impact of the entire EC2U Alliance.

The agenda was set up and developed as follows:

- 1) **Identify and Analyse Local Societal Demand:** Conduct a thorough massive survey to identify the specific needs and demands of local communities, including socioeconomic actors, university managers, researchers, professors, students, and other stakeholders. It aims at understanding their requirements and expectations in particular disciplines.
- 2) **Assess Research Capacities:** Evaluate the research capacities of RI4C2 partner universities, including research laboratories, research centres, and long and short-term R&I strategies. Understand the strengths and weaknesses of the existing research infrastructure and capabilities.
- 3) **Identify Common Ground:** Identify the common points between the demands of society and the research capacities of universities. Explore areas where societal demand aligns with the research strengths of the universities. Formulate a common research agenda that bridges the gap between societal needs and university research capacities.
- 4) **Establish new Virtual Institutes:** Based on the questionnaire identified research capacities, three new United Nations Global Goals (UNSDGs) were chosen to establish three new Virtual Institutes to address new specific topics. These Virtual Institutes will serve as collaborative platforms that bring together researchers, professors, students, and other stakeholders.

A. Mapping of R&I activities in EC2U Universities

This mapping of the R&I capacities of the seven universities of the EC2U Alliance was carried out by WP2 (EC2U R&I agenda) in cooperation with WP4 (EC2U R&I Platforms) and with the help of the R&I offices of each partner university.

This is a continuation of the work engaged by WP2 with the survey on R&I needs that was addressed to the seven university communities, the seven municipal and regional administrations, all EC2U associated partners and a selection of other economic, social and cultural stakeholders.

The process of data collection in the 7 universities for the mapping started in September 2022 and was completed in January 2023. In 4 of the universities, an on-site interview was conducted with the corresponding Vice-Rector/Director for Research. In those universities where it was not possible to carry out an on-site interview, a questionnaire was sent and answered by the relevant person in charge.

The information on research units that has been collected for the building of this mapping was also gradually supplied to WP4 for its transfer to the EC2U Connect Centre platform (<https://data.ec2u.eu/>).

This document consists in a first part dedicated to the R&I strategy of each university according to the information provided by the R&I offices and a second part that presents a mapping of the R&I facilities data extracted from the Connect Centre platform.

The results of the mapping and the survey were used to establish a common EC2U R&I Agenda for the next ten years. The priorities of this R&I Agenda will align with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3, 4, 11, 15 and 16 that are at the heart of both the existing Virtual Institutes and those that are being created.

This data base which maps all laboratories and research institutes within partner universities allows to quickly identify counterparts in order to build joint research projects.

[Link to the mapping of R&I activities](#)

B. EC2U Virtual Institutes

One of the objectives of the RI4C2 project is to define a common R&I agenda for the seven partner universities. This agenda will materialise with the creation of four new Virtual Institutes in addition to the three that were already created by EC2U.

In 2020, The EC2U Alliance launched Virtual Institutes aligned with above-mentioned SDGs. The Virtual Institutes within the EC2U Alliance are collaborative entities that transcend physical boundaries, bringing together international, interdisciplinary teams comprising students, teachers, researchers, and innovators from the seven partner universities. These institutes engage in a diverse array of training activities through and for research, including research mobilities, internships, summer/winter schools, and thematic workshops. The objective of the Virtual Institutes is to formulate innovative solutions to both local and global challenges.

In the first phase of the EC2U project, three Virtual Institutes were established, each aligned with specific SDGs. The three already existing Virtual Institutes are the following:

1) Virtual Institute for Good Health and Well-being (GLADE)

- Under the responsibility of the University of Iași (Romania)

GLADE aims at developing scientific cooperation in the field of SDG3 “Good Health and Well-Being”. It includes:

- The EC2U GLADE Literacy Lab, which organises conferences with experts of the EC2U network, summer schools and short video trainings.
- The EC2U GLADE Transformative Research Hub which initiates and supports research projects and develops recommendations for local authorities as well as guiding documents.
- The EC2U GLADE Healthy Campus Services that aim at developing a new approach to health on campuses.
- The *Joint Master's Programme in Lifelong Wellbeing and Healthy Ageing (LIFELINE)*.
- PhD training activities and thesis projects in co-supervision.

2) Virtual Institute for Quality Education (VIQE)

- Under the responsibility of the University of Salamanca (Spain)

VIQE develops activities that combines education, research and innovation for advanced studies in the field of SDG4 “Quality Education”.

This Virtual Institute leads the following activities:

- Language Policy Research Project.

The VIQE language policy research project studies current university language policies. The research team thus adopts a comparative approach to studying language policy practices. The research design is both qualitative and quantitative and incorporates research methods from the Humanities and Social Sciences, including the Digital Humanities.

- Research Seed Mobility Programme on Linguistic and Cultural Diversity

This programme aims at promoting mobilities between researchers and research units of the EC2U universities in the field of languages, cultures and societies. The objective is to form EC2U research groups, develop seed research projects and apply for additional national and EU funding.

- Joint doctoral training activities for existing doctoral programmes in the field of European languages and cultures.
- *Joint Master's programme in European Languages and Cultures in Contact.*
- PhD training activities and thesis projects in co-supervision.

3) Virtual Institute for Sustainable Cities and Communities (VISCC)

- Under the responsibility of the University of Coimbra (Portugal)

VISCC carries out activities in the field of SDG11 “Sustainable Cities and Communities” that promote interdisciplinarity, collaborative work and mobility between the EC2U partner universities, the cities and the citizens.

The activities of this Virtual Institute include:

- *A Joint Master's Degree in Sustainable Cities and Communities.*
- PhD training activities and thesis projects in co-supervision.
- Online courses.
- Winter and Summer Schools.
- Research projects.

The RI4C2 project involves the creation of four new Virtual Institutes in addition to the three existing ones. Several instruments were used to identify topics for these four Institutes:

- A questionnaire about R&I needs targeting the seven partner universities communities (managers, researchers, doctoral students, students, staff members).
- A mapping of R&I activities and infrastructures in the seven partner universities.
- Discussions with Vice-Rectors for Research and local RI4C2 teams.

These instruments allowed to identify topics that align with the objectives, priorities and capacities of the partner institutions to constitute the foundations of four new Institutes:

4) Virtual Institute for Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions

Within the framework of the EC2U consolidation phase (2023-2027), a fourth Virtual Institute related to SDG16 "Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions" is being created.

5) Division of the Virtual Institute for Quality Education

Considering the large spectrum of activities within this SDG and the new activities developed in the EC2U consolidation phase, it was decided to split this Virtual Institute in two:

- Virtual Institute for Quality Education (Modern languages)
- Virtual Institute for Quality Education (Digital pedagogies)

6) Creation of the Virtual Institute for Life on land

A consensus emerged in favour of establishing a new Virtual Institute characterised by strong interdisciplinary collaboration, specifically centred around SDG15 "Life on Land". This Virtual Institute will focus on the environmental aspects connected to climate change.

7) Creation of the Virtual Institute Materials and Methods for a Sustainable Future

A suggestion was made to create a fourth Virtual Institute in the field of natural sciences, such as chemistry and physics, that are currently underrepresented in the Virtual Institutes portfolios. This Virtual Institute aims at exploring how natural sciences can contribute to building a sustainable future.

Figure 2: EC2U Virtual Institutes

8) Creation of an eight Virtual Institute

An eight Virtual Institute led by the Johannes Kepler University of Linz will be created.

V. WP3 – EC2U People empowerment

Researchers play a crucial role in advancing scientific knowledge, driving innovation, improving quality of life, and enhancing the competitiveness of Europe. The goal of Work Package 3 is to enhance the capacity of the EC2U Alliance to support its researchers, from undergraduate to senior levels, in their career development. This includes providing professional recognition, tools, and training, as well as promoting balanced mobility (physical, virtual, blended) across the EC2U pan-European campus and ensuring equal opportunities for all.

A. Masterclasses on gender equality in R&I

To effectively tackle the issue of gender imbalance and empower all genders, RI4C2 developed Masterclasses. These Masterclasses are designed by drawing upon the vast array of Gender resources and programmes offered by the EC2U Alliance. The Masterclasses provide practical and concrete guidance on how to implement Gender Equality policies, procedures, and behaviours in research and innovation activities.

1) Masterclass *Gender equality and Inclusive Communication in Research & Innovation Activities*

- **Summary**

Higher education institutions are in a strategic position to create and implement recommendations for Gender Equality. Going beyond the focus on interpersonal actions, there must be a strategic recognition of structural issues that create barriers to an equitable and inclusive environment, which recognises and responds to the diversity of lived experiences and existing identities.

This Masterclass discusses Gender Equality and Inclusive Communication in R&I activities addressing practical aspects that can contribute to improving everyday practice in teaching, supervising, mentoring, and researching.

- **Expert Biography**

This Masterclass was presented by Rita Alcaire, who is an anthropologist, documentary filmmaker, and social science communicator working at the intersection of social sciences, media and arts. She is a postdoctoral researcher at the Centre for Social Studies at the University of Coimbra. She holds a PhD in Human Rights and a MA in Cultural Psychiatry. Her research interests

lie in the study of gender and sexualities, mental health, and pop culture using the media as a privileged way to engage with them.

- **Links to recording**

Available at:

[EC2U Website](#)

[EC2U Alliance YouTube Channel](#)

2) Masterclass *The Ethics of Gender Equality in Science and Research*

- **Summary**

The second Gender Equality masterclass aims to address the gender gap in science through an ethical research approach. It provides an overview of relevant data, current policies, and best practices, offering insights into one of the primary contemporary challenges in research.

- **Expert Biography**

The speaker for this masterclass is Daniela Ovidia, an Italian science journalist, neuroscientist, and neuroethicist. She studied medicine and neuroscience at Università Statale in Milan, Italy, and neuroethics at the University of Pennsylvania in Philadelphia, US. She serves as the Co-director of the Neuroscience and Society Lab at the University of Pavia and is also the Scientific Director of Agenzia Zoe, an agency specialising in science journalism and writing.

Furthermore, she holds the position of professor in subjects such as “Ethics of Research and Responsible Research and Innovation” for doctoral students, “Neuroethics,” and “Communication of Neuroscience” for undergraduate students in Psychology at the University of Pavia in Italy.

- **Links to recording**

Available at:

[EC2U Website](#)

[EC2U Alliance YouTube Channel](#)

3) Masterclass *Fostering gender equality at the university through policy and practice*

- **Summary**

The first part of the masterclass presents some of the measures and actions recently introduced by the University of Poitiers to promote gender equality and diversity, and to combat

discrimination. The description of this structurally unfinished and increasingly demanding task is also an opportunity to share experiences and reflect, not only on how to think about a policy of substantive equality, but also on the role of the university in the contemporary world.

The second part of the Masterclass aims to highlight women's career paths in research and entrepreneurship, and to address stereotypes and gender inequality in these fields. It provides an overview of the “Sciences En Mouvement d'Elles” project through the account of Albane Rozenholc, a PhD student at the University of Poitiers, who is involved in this initiative.

- **Experts biographies**

The speaker of the first part of the masterclass is Catherine Rannoux. She is a Professor of French and stylistics at the University of Poitiers. In charge of the equality and diversity task force, she leads the gender equality and anti-discrimination policy at the University of Poitiers. She is also President of the select academic board, which is in charge of all matters related to teachers and researchers' careers at the University of Poitiers.

The speaker of the second part of the masterclass is Albane Rozenholc. She is a PhD Student in Microbiology and Molecular biology at the University of Poitiers, School of Medicine and Pharmacy, in unit UMR 1070 “Pharmacology of Antimicrobial Agents”.

- **Links to recording**

Available at:

[EC2U Website](#)

[EC2U Alliance YouTube Channel](#)

B. Toolkit for Researcher Career Development

The objective of the EC2U Alliance is to create a common online platform that aggregates skills and career development resources, with a focus on promoting cross-regional and cross-sectoral mobility to make reflections on how to do a better career management in academia, research and innovation. To support the achievement of this aim, a toolkit for Researcher Career Development was designed, which promotes “Career Reflections” through showcases of academic career options, assessments of geographical and inter-sectoral mobility prospects, and opportunities within the EC2U Alliance.

[Link to the toolkit](#)

VI. WP 4 – EC2U R&I platforms

WP4 is in charge of the technical digital platform that facilitates the seamless exchange of information among the partner universities within the EC2U Alliance through shared databases. This platform expands the reach of the EC2U Connect Centre (along with its Knowledge Hub) to encompass the R&I missions of the RI4C2 project. Moreover, it plays a crucial role in supporting other Work Packages in disseminating various resources, such as masterclasses, MOOCs, guidebooks, and other relevant materials related to gender equality, Open Science, Citizen Science, and R&I capacity of the partners to a wider audience. This platform enables efficient collaboration and knowledge-sharing, strengthening the digital infrastructure and capabilities of the Alliance, enabling effective implementation of its R&I missions.

A. R&I capacities database

The R&I capacities database aims at mapping the R&I facilities within the EC2U Alliance in order to foster mobilities, facilitate knowledge sharing and encourage collaboration around joint research projects (see [IV.A](#)).

The database identifies and provides background information about research and innovation units and supporting structures at EC2U partner universities.

[Link to the R&I capacities database](#)

B. Researcher Career database

Work Package 4 (WP4), by using data provided by the seven universities, is collecting in a database all the available information and digital documents on topics that have an impact on researchers' career. A first list of topics has been selected during the draft phase of the project and includes:

- Supervisor development
- Academic diplomacy
- Project planning & management
- Information on academic publishing
- Academic writing
- Leadership

- Teaching
- Ethics of research and R&I impact assessment
- Branding of academic skills
- Overview on research career paths or options
- Technology transfer
- Labour market for researchers
- Entrepreneurship

More topics will be added during the consolidation phase of the EC2U Alliance.

The aim of the database is to collect information on policy documents produced by the partner universities and display them according to a common taxonomy.

This searchable database will allow policy makers and researchers to retrieve and compare the documents to evaluate the differences among the member institutions, identify gaps in policing and promote common policing to harmonise the researchers' careers as much as possible, together with the harmonisation of good ethical and behavioural practices.

In the consolidation phase of the EC2U Alliance, this database will be the first core of a larger database on academic policing. The future development of the digital infrastructure will allow the use of AI tools to analyse, summarise and compare documents available only in local languages.

[Link to the Research career database](#)

C. Knowledge ecosystems database

A Knowledge Ecosystem consists of users and producers of knowledge, organised around a joint object of research/challenge that needs to be solved.

The EC2U Knowledge Ecosystem Dataset is the result of the survey conducted by WP6 to map the Local Knowledge Ecosystems as key actors involved in Research and Innovation processes.

The database is aimed at mapping all the actors within the consortium in order to facilitate partnership and knowledge sharing, research projects and applications.

The mapping of the Citizen science initiatives, also included in the dataset, aims to deliver the prizes for Citizen Science Champions, a delivery of WP6.

Link to the [Knowledge ecosystem database](#)

D. Open Science database and platform

This platform will allow the sharing of WP7 results among the seven universities. It is part of the Toolkit for Researcher's Career Development. It is available at the following [link](#).

E. Open access repository

An Open access repository for the EC2U Alliance was created, in agreement with practices and regulations at the different universities and European level. It is available at the following [link](#).

VII. WP5 – EC2U Innovation Sphere

A. EC2U Virtual Lecture Series Innovation

This lecture series encourages a wide and critical understanding of innovation – from incremental to disruptive types of innovation, from technological to social innovations. It gives voice to various stakeholders from academia and industry within the innovation sphere that highlight different aspects of innovation. The Virtual Lecture Series Innovation aims at different target groups – interested citizens, students, and professionals from university and industry.

Episode 1: Innovation – so important but hard to predict or On how to outsmart uncertainty

Speaker:

Prof. Dr. Uwe Cantner, professor of microeconomics, Vice President for Young Researchers and Diversity Management at the University of Jena, and chairman of the Expert Commission on Research and Innovation (EFI) of the German federal government

[Link to the episode](#)

Episode 2: Sustainable and Circular Entrepreneurship

Speakers:

Beatrice Re, post-doctoral researcher at the University of Pavia

Alberto Bressan as guest of honor, founder of the circular fashion company SEAY

[Link to the episode](#)

Episode 3: Social Innovation: The dynamics of companies, society and territories towards social innovations

Speakers:

Prof. Dominique Royoux, professor of geography and Co-Chairman of the Joint Research Unit “DESTINS”

Ursula Dechein, research engineer at “DESTINS”

Sébastien Palluault, Co-founder of the Company “Ellyx” and Member of the Executive Committee of “DESTINS”

[Link to the episode](#)

Episode 4: A new level in industry-university collaboration: The Entrepreneurs in Residence (EiR) programme at the University of Turku

Speakers:

Laura Strömberg, Founder and CEO of Dagsmark Petfoodn EiR.

Jussi Karttila, Founder and CEO of Zefort, EiR.

Jarna Heinonen, Professor of Entrepreneurship
Sanna Ilonen, University teacher in Entrepreneurship

[Link to the episode](#)

Episode 5: Innovative Strategies for the Development of New Research Ideas

Speakers:

Jorge Noro, Executive Coordinator of Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of University of Coimbra

Ana Santos Carvalho, Science Communication Coordinator at Institute of Interdisciplinary Research of University of Coimbra

[Link to the episode](#)

Episode 6: Innovation in agriculture – Agriculture 4.0

Speakers:

Diego González-Aguilera, Professor of Engineering at the University of Salamanca and Director of the TIDOP Research Unit.

Luis Enrique Corredera, Director of Innovation and Digital Transformation at *Deloitte*

Raúl García Serrada, Project Manager at the Air Institute USAL.

Óscar Lorenzo, Rector's Delegate for Transfer and Innovation and Professor of Botany at the University of Salamanca

[Link to the episode](#)

Episode 7: Intangible innovation

Speakers:

Catalin Vrabier, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration Bucharest

Valentina Diana Rusu, Institute for Interdisciplinary Research, Alexandra Ioan Cuza University of Iași

[Link to the episode](#)

B. Recipes of Innovation – An EC2U Cookbook

- **Rationale**

The Lighthouses of Innovation have an important role to play in the EC2U Pan-European Knowledge Ecosystem (PEKE). They encompass a wide range of entities, including academic institutions, research projects and initiatives, businesses, innovation and technology transfer organisations, as well as local authorities and administrative bodies. They represent a broad perspective on innovation and excel in identifying and creating possibilities. Collectively and

individually, they play a key role in shaping a collaborative European research and innovation agenda. To kick off the co-creation of the publication, two workshops were held as two virtual and interactive events (20/06 and 27/06/2022). A summarising video of the sessions is available on the [EC2U website](#).

“Recipes of Innovation. An EC2U Cookbook” is the title of the publication jointly prepared by the RI4C2 project teams. The publication showcases best practices from partner universities and summarises the workshops of the Lighthouses of Innovation. It aims at supporting innovation among students, researchers and others and encourage the connection of ideas from the world of science to everyday life applications. Moreover, it aims to show different ways for academic and non-academic actors to connect and to create value for society together. In addition, the publication is a means to make the innovation support structures and the Lighthouses of Innovation more visible. The target group of the publication are all students and researchers within the EC2U Alliance and beyond, other Lighthouses of Innovation as well as the governance bodies of the EC2U universities and interested citizens.

The "Recipes of Innovation" are a collection of insights and best practices drawn from the experience and expertise of the so-called “Lighthouses of Innovation.”

- **Outline of the publication**

The “Recipes of Innovation” are divided into two parts:

- **Part 1** contains central ideas that emerged from the workshops with the Lighthouses of Innovation and is written as a series of questions to the Lighthouses:
 - Lighthouses of Innovation, who are your hungry customers?
 - Lighthouses of Innovation, which appliances do you need to transform the ingredients into tasty meals?
 - Lighthouses of Innovation, what are your challenges while cooking?
 - Lighthouses of Innovation, what are the three top ingredients for successful innovation?
- **Part 2** contains the best practices fostering innovation and innovative thinking in the following categories:
 - Awareness-rising
 - Networking,

- Start-up collaboration
- Other.

[Link to the Recipes of Innovation](#)

C. Makeathon

A Makeathon is an engaging and interactive event that brings together participants to collaboratively develop creative solutions within a designated time frame. The primary goal of our Makeathon is to highlight the innovative ability of both the EC2U Alliance and the individual universities and cities involved, while also fostering the creation and implementation of ideas that contribute to a more sustainable future.

The Makeathon involves local actors from each city of the EC2U Alliance:

- **Multidisciplinary teams of participants:** Students, pupils, citizens, employees, entrepreneurs, and others who actively engage in the Makeathon to solve a challenge creatively.
- **Challenge-givers:** Organisations, companies, or individuals who propose specific challenges or problem statements for participants to address during the Makeathon. They define the problems, objectives, and requirements of the challenges, providing participants with a clear focus for their solution development.
- **Mentors:** Experts or professionals with specialized knowledge who provide guidance, feedback, and advice to participants, helping them refine their ideas and navigate challenges.
- **A jury:** A panel of experts who assess and evaluate the solutions presented by teams, considering criteria such as creativity, feasibility, sustainability, and potential impact.

The first edition of the EC2U Makeathon was entitled « Reinvent the Future ». It was organised on May 6th and 7th 2024 as a hybrid event. It was divided in six local tracks that took place at in six different EC2U cities and one virtual European track. Local teams worked on-site in each EC2U city while European teams worked online. The seven tracks were connected through a livestream and via regular online check-ins. The Makeathon nurtured collaboration among local

and European stakeholders who share the same mission: solving societal challenge, driving progress and change.

Four areas were advanced via concrete challenges:

Figure 2: Thematic areas for the Makeathon

After 24 hours of preparation, brainstorming, and teamwork, each local team, with the help of mentors, presented their projects to the local juries who selected the “local winners”. As the aim was to emphasise innovation and collaboration more than competition, each team received an honorable mention from the jury based their project’s specific characteristics. In addition, the local winners were awarded with a grant to travel to Poitiers to present their project in front of European Commission representatives and stakeholders of the EC2U community at the RI4C2 closing event in June 2024.

More information about the event is available on [our website](#).

The EC2U Makeathon will be organised every other year. The next edition will take place in 2026.

VIII. WP6 – EC2U Knowledge Ecosystems

A. Introducing Living Labs

The promotion of Citizen Science is one of the central objectives of the RI4C2 project. It is also one of the main orientations of the European Union in the field of research. With the objective to encourage participative research and innovation processes involving the seven universities and local actors and citizens, the RI4C2 project included the creation of Living Labs within the EC2U Virtual Institutes. Below, the concept and objectives of the Living Labs are defined and the steps of their creation are introduced.

- **What is a Living Lab?**

The first Living Labs experiments were implemented in Northern Europe with the development of cooperative design with involvement of the public (in the 1970s). In the rest of Europe, digital initiatives that connected citizens, businesses and policymakers were developed in the 1980s and 1990s. The concept of Living Lab appeared in academic discussions in the 1990s, but it gained momentum only in 2006, when the European Commission launched an initiative to promote and coordinate a Common European Innovation System based on Living Labs.

There are various definitions and conceptualisations of Living Labs. However, three essential components can be identified as constituting the basis of the Living Lab concept: (1) a co-creation process involving a large set of stakeholders, (2) in real-life sites and (3) involving the end-user.

Thus, a Living Lab can be defined as open R&I ecosystem that is centred on the end-user and based on a cocreation approach involving R&I processes within local communities and their territories aiming at generating a durable impact that addresses the expectations and needs of the local communities. Citizens, inhabitants and users are considered as key actors of R&I processes.

Active User Involvement

A Living Lab involves relevant stakeholders actively in all relevant activities, ensuring their feedback is captured and implemented throughout the whole lifecycle of the innovation.

Multi Stakeholder Participation

Taking a holistic view on society, involving stakeholders from the government, academia, private sectors and citizens.

Orchestration

The Living Lab operates as the orchestrator within the ecosystem to connect and partner up with relevant stakeholders.

Co-creation

In a Living Lab, values are bottom-up co-created not only for but also by all relevant stakeholders, ensuring a higher adoption at the end.

Real Life Setting

A Living Lab operates in the real-life setting of the end users, infusing innovations into their real life instead of moving the user to test sites to explore the innovations

Multi Method Approach

Each Living Lab activity is problem driven. Therefore, the methodological approach towards every individual activity will be selected based on the expected outcomes of the activity and the stakeholders who needs to be involved.

Figure 3: Six building blocks of a Living Lab, adapted from ENoLL (enoll.org)

Figure 4: Innovation cycle of the Living Lab

- **The EC2U Living Labs**

One of the RI4C2 project activities is focused on “EC2U Knowledge Ecosystems” and aims at developing an action plan for Citizen Science including the identification of Citizen Science Champions locally involved in Citizen Science research projects. Concretely, this action plan will materialise with the creation of Living Labs within each of the three existing EC2U Virtual Institutes.

The topics of the three Living Labs were identified using several instruments:

- The “Citizen Science and Knowledge Ecosystem” survey, which aimed at identifying local stakeholders involved in Citizen Science activities and their field of expertise.
- Seven focus-groups organised with the Citizen Science Champions in each of the seven Local Knowledge Ecosystems
- Two World Cafés with the representatives of the EC2U / RI4C2 partner universities

- One World Café with the scientific coordinators of the EC2U Virtual institutes

This process resulted in the identification of three interdisciplinary and stimulating topics that are supported by the local knowledge ecosystem actors involved.

- Topic for the Living Lab of the GLADE Virtual Institute: Healthy (Home) Office Habits
- Topic for the Living Lab of the VIQE Virtual Institute: Teaching Languages in Communities and Approaching Cultural Biases from Multiple Perspectives
- Topic for the Living Lab of the VISCC Virtual Institute: Perceptions of Building Environment. Indoor Environment and Quality of Air.

1) GLADE Living Lab – Healthy (Home) Office Habits

Within the GLADE Virtual Institute, the Living Lab will implement activities dedicated to preventing health problems and promoting a healthy and active lifestyle. It will address issues related to aging, lifestyle, well-being and other themes related to Healthy (Home) Office Habits.

A collaboration is being built with the « QG Habitudes de vie - Sport Santé », a resource centre located in Poitiers, led by Laurent Bosquet (MOVE laboratory), and dedicated to the promotion of health through life habits. This structure includes a gymnasium, a teaching kitchen, a fitness room, training/meeting rooms, and innovative equipment.

The « La Vie La Santé » structure of the Poitiers Hospital, in collaboration with Marion Albouy (EBI laboratory), was also identified as a partner for a future Citizen Science project within the GLADE Living Lab. This structure offers support and workshops for citizens and patients to adopt adequate life habits that support their health in all its dimensions (physical, mental and social).

The project led by Laurent Bosquet in collaboration with Marion Albouy, IN MOTION (Better agING at hOME: an internaTIONal living lab on lifehabits and health), received funding from UP-SQUARED – PARI (Funding programme at the University of Poitiers) to develop the Living Lab activities. The next step is to identify researchers and stakeholders within partner universities who would like to get involved in the project.

2) VIQE Living Lab - Teaching Languages in Communities and Approaching Cultural Biases from Multiple Perspectives

This Living Lab aims at developing activities that will apply research methods from the Humanities and Social Sciences, including the Digital Humanities, from multiple perspectives. This project is being developed in collaboration with all partner universities. The objective is to identify researchers and stakeholders who could participate in this Living Lab but also call for projects to develop its first activities.

3) VISCC Living Lab - Perceptions of Building Environment. Indoor Environment and Quality of Air.

This Living Lab focuses on scientific activities that promote interdisciplinarity and collaborative work around the topic of *Perceptions of building environment - Indoor environment and quality of air*. This project is being developed in collaboration with all partner universities. A project (via National Romanian funding) was submitted by the University of Iasi to start developing this Living Lab's activities.

- **Next steps of the development of the Living Labs**

The current objective for VIQE and VISCC (described in figure 5) Living Labs is to **identify researchers among all partner universities who work on the selected topics** to develop research projects with a Citizen Science approach. Once the teams are constituted for each Living Lab, they will be able to **answer project calls** to secure funding to implement planned activities.

Figure 5: Topics of the VIQE and VISCC Living Labs

- **Opportunities for researchers**

The Living Labs offer several types of opportunities to researchers:

- Improving the visibility of researchers and their activities
- Finding European partners
- Securing local, national and European funding
- Implementing research projects with and for citizens in collaboration with EC2U European partners
- Sharing good practices for Citizen Science with EC2U partners

- **Contacts and useful information**

Friday, February 16th, 2024 – Conference for the launch of the EC2U Living Labs

An online conference was organised on February 16th, 2024 to present the Living Labs and constitute the network of actors who will be involved in the Living Labs.

More information on the Living Labs and the conference are available on [the website of the Alliance](#).

Participating in future RI4C2 Living Lab activities

If you are interested in getting involved in future RI4C2 living labs activities, we invite you to contact:

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IX. WP7- Open Science

WP7 aims to promote the dissemination of Open Science principles and practices by creating educational resources, such as a Guidebook on Open Science practices. By producing educational materials, EC2U empowers its researchers with the knowledge and skills needed to embrace Open Science principles and practices. This contributes to a culture of openness, transparency, and collaboration within the EC2U community, leading to improved research practices, increased research impact, and enhanced innovation. Moreover, it fosters a sense of ownership and engagement among EC2U citizens in shaping the future of science and society.

A. Open Science guidebook

Open Science aims to make scientific outputs and processes open, transparent and reproducible. Sharing the benefits of Open Science practices with researchers and supporting them to develop their skills and knowledge is still needed.

Therefore, an Open Science guidebook was created, which is a general-level and non-commercial practical online guide for researchers looking for information and tips on how to approach a range of Open Science practices. It offers guidance and resources especially for researchers but also for any other person interested in improving levels of openness in research practices. The EC2U partner universities will have the possibility to use this guidebook in their organisational support activities freely. The guide may be published on the partner organisations' respective websites.

Overall, this guidebook supports the EC2U partner universities in developing a broader and a more practical perspective towards supporting researchers in meeting the current requirements of Open Science. It addresses two of the most established Open Science practices; open access publishing and open data, and two emerging ones; open workflows and Open Science communities.

The guidebook consists of the practical guidelines which are supplemented by interviews of the Open Science Champions.

[Link to the Open Science guidebook](#)

[Link to the interviews](#)

B. Online Open Science resource platform

WP4 created a resource platform devoted to Open Science practices and tools created in WP7. It is part of the Toolkit for Researchers' Career Development. This platform is available at the following [link](#).

C. Masterclasses on Open Science

Four introductory videos and two podcast episodes on a selection of Open Science practices were produced. A compilation of short videos where stakeholders from each partner university answers the question "why is Open Science important" is also available and gives the possibility to discover different perspectives on Open Science within the EC2U Alliance.

Video 1: Why is Open Science important?

Description: This first video is a multilingual video on the importance of open science. The experts from the partner universities of the EC2U alliance share their views on why open science is important in their native languages.

Video 2: Pre-registration: What does it actually bring us?

Description: Senior Research Fellow Lydia Laninga-Wijnen from the INVEST Flagship, University of Turku explains the benefits and challenges related to pre-registration and along the way also shares some insights how to write pre-registrations and what tools can be used.

Video 3: Open Science for scientists and opening science for non-scientists

Description: Postdoctoral researcher Smriti Mehta from the University of California, Berkeley talks about Open Science, what science is and what it could be and along the way also shares some examples of projects she is involved in that support open science practices.

Video 4: Baby steps for reproducible workflow in R – part 1: introduction

Description: Senior researcher Juuso Repo from the University of Turku gives an introduction in this first part to what is reproducibility and why do we need it and guides us through the steps for reproducible workflow in R. In part 2 he will show a hands-on demo in RStudio.

Video 5: Baby steps for reproducible workflow in R – part 2: demo

Description: Senior researcher Juuso Repo from the University of Turku shares in this second part a hands-on demo in RStudio showing in action the steps introduced in the part 1.

In addition to the videos, the Masterclasses are complemented by two podcast episodes:

- **How open workflows increase impact and enhance open science?**
- **How to make science more tangible for a broader audience?**

The videos and podcasts are openly accessible and suitable for anyone interested in the wide range of Open Science topics covered in the materials.

[Link to the videos of the Masterclasses on Open Science](#)

[Link to the podcast "How open workflows increase impact and enhance open science?"](#)

[Link to the podcast "How to make science more tangible for a broader audience?"](#)

X. WP8 – Transformation Dissemination

WP8 aims at promoting the RI4C2 project and PEKE to key stakeholders, including representatives from the European Commission, other European Universities Alliances and important actors from the EC2U PEKE as well as potential new partners. It aims at making the project and its results known to a wider audience, mainly during the EC2U Forum which take place each year.

Moreover, with the coordination of FOREU2 (Forum of the Alliances funded in 2020), it aims at sharing good practices and progress on the implementation of R&I long-term strategies. Indeed, the 24 Alliances from the second Erasmus+ Pilot Call (Athena, Aurora Alliance, Circle U, E3UDRES2, EC2U, EELISA, ENGAGE.EU, ENHANCE, ENLIGHT, ERUA, EUNICE, EUniWell, EURECA-PRO, EuroTeQ, Eut, FILMEU, INVEST, NeurotechEU, RUN-EU, T4E, ULYSSEUS, UNIC, UNITA, UNIVERSEH), have agreed by the time of submission that they will build a collaboration network with the creation of a “Forum of European Universities #2 – FOREU2” where they discuss and share intelligence (via regular face-to-face or on-line meetings) resulting from:

- Assessment of current and best practices and progress made (incl. success stories) in the implementation of R&I long-term strategies;
- Special focus on practices and measures taken/to be taken to ensure the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies;
- Identification of obstacles – legal, financial and regulatory – existing at different scales (local, regional or European).

A. Joint FOREU2 report on gender equality

This report aims at addressing the issue of gender equality in R&I via case studies taken from 16 H2020 SwafS projects of European University Alliances. The purpose is to share measures (already implemented or ongoing) at university or at Alliances levels to ensure the mainstreaming of the gender equality dimension in R&I long-term strategies. The case studies serve as examples of good practices to inspire individual universities and Alliances to make continuous progress in this area.

The deliverable first presents an overview of the participating universities and of the policy framework for gender equality defined by the European Union. Each case study is then

described in details. Finally, the last section outlines the main findings drawn out from all case studies and offers recommendations for possible measures to be implemented to improve the mainstreaming of gender equality in R&I.

[Link to the First FOREU2 report on gender equality](#)

B. D8.8 FOREU2 report on the implementation of R&I long term strategies

In this second joint report, different types of strategies and activities implemented in order to foster the development of R&I within Alliances are presented via case studies provided by 20 H2020 SwafS projects awarded to European University Alliances.

The report focuses first on the context and participant Alliances. Case studies are then presented within three distinct topical categories: one concerns political strategies, another includes operational features, and the last topic deals with various other relevant good practices. Finally, the last section presents the key elements and lessons-learned from the case studies included in this report.

[Link to the second joint FOREU2 report](#)

XI. Contacts

For more information on the activities of the RI4C2 project, you can contact:

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For more information, you can also visit <https://ec2u.eu/ri4c2/>

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